

POSSIBILITIES OF ULTRASOUND APPLICATION IN CONVECTIVE DRYING OF FOOD PRODUCTS

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Convection drying of foodstuffs still has some limitations that make it difficult to apply in certain areas. These include slow drying rate and loss of product quality. Some of these limitations can be overcome by introducing new technologies used as additional energy sources. Among others, ultrasound stands out, which is able to influence the drying rate without causing a significant increase in the temperature of the material. This favours its application in the drying of various temperature-sensitive materials or in drying processes carried out at low temperatures, such as convection drying at atmospheric pressure [1].

Acoustic energy is one of the fundamental forms of energy found in nature. Sound waves are elastic mechanical vibrations of medium particles propagating in time and space. Unlike electromagnetic waves such as microwaves, sound waves require a material medium (solid, liquid or gaseous) for their propagation, as their transmission is due to elastic deformations of matter. Thus, in a vacuum where there are no material particles, sound propagation is impossible, while electromagnetic waves can be freely transmitted in such a medium due to their nature, which does not depend on the presence of matter [2].

Ultrasound is acoustic waves with a frequency exceeding the upper threshold of audibility of the human ear - about 20 kHz. This classification is conditional and is based solely on the physiological peculiarities of human perception of sound, not on physical differences. From the physical point of view, ultrasonic waves obey the same basic laws of generation, propagation and interaction with materials as sounds in the audible range, since the principles of acoustics remain unchanged across the entire frequency spectrum [3].

The presence of ultrasound in nature is quite widespread. Some animals have a hearing limit in the ultrasonic frequency range. For example, the upper limit for dogs is 50 kHz and up to 100 kHz for bats and dolphins. Communication

of these animals with the environment is largely based on the use of ultrasound [4].

In 1880, the Curie couple discovered the piezoelectric effect, a phenomenon on which some modern ultrasound generation systems are based, so this date can be considered the date of the beginning of ultrasound [5].

Galton in 1883 developed the first ultrasonic transducer, which was a whistle used to explore the limits of human hearing. The first commercial application of ultrasound was the "Echo sounder" [6].

Ultrasonic parameters.

Ultrasonic waves, like all types of mechanical waves, are described by a set of physical parameters that determine their behaviour and interaction with the medium. The main characteristics include frequency, wavelength, amplitude, propagation velocity, intensity, and acoustic impedance. These parameters determine the properties of ultrasound during its generation, propagation and interaction with different materials, and play a key role in the choice of modes in practical applications such as medical diagnostics, defectoscopy or material processing (Fig. 1) [2].

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic wave propagation

Frequency (f, Hz). The frequency of a wave is defined as the number of oscillations or cycles made by the wave per unit of time. The International System of Units uses hertz (Hz), which is defined as the number of cycles a wave makes in one second. The inverse of frequency is called the period and is defined as the time it takes for a wave to complete one cycle.

Wavelength (λ, m). The wavelength is the distance between two planes in which the particles are in the same state of oscillation, i.e. the distance between two consecutive points vibrating in phase. It is determined from the velocity and frequency of the wave (1).

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f} \tag{1}$$

Velocity (c, m/s). Acoustic velocity is the speed of propagation of waves. The propagation velocity of longitudinal and transverse waves is characteristic of the material and can generally be considered constant for a given material, although it can be affected by environmental variables such as temperature and pressure.

Amplitude (A, m) is the maximum displacement of a particle of the medium from its equilibrium position under the influence of an ultrasonic wave, which determines the intensity and energy of the oscillatory process.

Sound pressure (PA, N/m²). Sound pressure is the pressure in different zones of a material. This pressure will be higher than normal in zones of particle compression and lower in zones of particle expansion, hence acoustic pressure is variable. The maximum deviation from normal is called the amplitude of the acoustic pressure and is related to the amplitude of the oscillation of the wave.

Noise intensity (I, W/m²). The intensity of an acoustic wave is defined as the average energy transmitted through a unit area perpendicular to the direction of wave propagation per unit time. The intensity of an acoustic wave is proportional to the square of the maximum sound pressure (2).

$$I = \frac{P_A^2}{2\rho c} \quad (2)$$

Energy density (E, J/m³). During wave propagation, energy is transferred and can be dissipated as heat due to the work expended to move particles in a medium subject to forces that counteract the movement of the particles. Energy density can be expressed as the ratio of the intensity of acoustic radiation to the speed of wave propagation (3).

$$E = \frac{I}{c} \quad (3)$$

Energy density is measured in units of J/m³. If energy is expressed in Newtons per metre (Nm), energy density units are converted to N/m², i.e. pressure units. In other words, energy density is equivalent to sound pressure level.

Sound power (P, W). Acoustic power is the total energy emitted by the ultrasound source per unit time. It can be calculated from the intensity of acoustic radiation and the area of the radiating surface (4).

$$P = I \cdot S \quad (4)$$

Power can be expressed in decibels as the logarithmic ratio between the existing acoustic intensity (or power) in the environment and the reference acoustic intensity (or power) (5).

$$P_{dB} = 10 \log \frac{I}{I_0} \quad (5)$$

Like power, sound pressure can be denoted in decibels (6).

$$P_{AdB} = 10 \log \frac{P_A^2}{P_{A0}^2} \quad (6)$$

here I_0 is usually taken to be 1×10^{-12} (W/m²); P_{A0} is usually taken to be 2×10^{-5} (Pa).

Acoustic impedance (Z). It is defined as the ratio of acoustic pressure to the vibration velocity of the particle. It is a very important parameter that determines the fraction of energy that is reflected and transmitted when an acoustic wave changes medium. Like light, when an ultrasonic wave hits an interface, some of it is reflected and some of it is transmitted. The fraction of energy reflected depends largely on the difference in impedance between the two media. The greater this difference, the more energy reflected and the less energy transmitted. This characteristic is of great importance in ultrasonic applications.

Attenuation. When an ultrasonic wave propagates in a medium, the intensity of the wave decreases with increasing distance from the source of the wave. This phenomenon is known as attenuation. Equation (7) gives an expression for calculating the intensity of an acoustic wave at a point located at a certain distance (d) from the source of radiation.

$$I = I_0 \exp(-\alpha_a d) \quad (7)$$

Attenuation can be the result of reflection, scattering or diffraction of a wave during propagation, as well as the conversion of part of the wave's kinetic energy into heat. Attenuation becomes more important as the frequency of the wave increases due to the increase in the attenuation coefficient (α_a).

Classification of acoustic waves.

Acoustic waves are classified by frequency in the range from 20 Hz to 20 kHz. Waves with frequencies below 20 Hz are called subsonic and those above 20 kHz are called ultrasonic (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Classification of sound by frequency

In terms of industrial applications, ultrasonic waves are classified based on their frequency and energy characteristics [2].

There are two main types: power ultrasound (or high intensity ultrasound) and signalling ultrasound (or low intensity ultrasound). Power ultrasound covers a frequency range of 20 to 100 kHz at intensities greater than 1 W/cm².

Due to their high acoustic energy, these waves are able to induce physicochemical changes in the materials being processed or actively influence technological processes. Signal ultrasound is characterised by frequencies from 100 kHz to 20 MHz and intensities of less than 1 W/cm².

Application of ultrasound in drying food products.

The use of ultrasound in convection drying of food products such as beetroot, pumpkin and others significantly increases the efficiency of the process. The results of our research show that the use of ultrasound with a frequency of 25< kHz can reduce the time of convection drying by 35% by facilitating the internal migration of moisture. In addition, better colour retention and less structural shrinkage of plant tissue are observed. The combination of ultrasound and hot air (at 50 °C) improves the porosity of the product, allowing more efficient rehydration. These advantages make ultrasound a promising tool for optimising beetroot drying [7].

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